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Problems of Translating phrasal verbs from English to Uzbek**Makhmudjonova Diana Oybek qizi**

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Abstract: When we translate verbs, we encounter significant difficulties, especially between structurally and culturally different languages, such as English and Uzbek. In particular, phrasal verbs play an important role in the lexical system of modern English. They represent the stylistic richness of natural colloquial speech and its national identity. Phrasal verbs are one of the most complex and at the same time the most meaningful elements of the English language. Because their meaning is not translated literally, but is understood idiomatic, that is, in a context-specific way. Therefore, semantic, stylistic and cultural problems arise in the process of translating them. These features, their types and the main problems encountered in translating into Uzbek are analyzed. The relevance of the study is that it provides advice on the main factors determining the quality of translation, the correct interpretation of phrasal verbs in the process of learning English and translating, and understanding their idiomatic meaning.

Keywords: Compound verbs, translation problems, idiomatic expression, semantics, context, equivalent, phraseological unit, lexical unit, polysemanticity.

Introduction.

Phrasal verbs, which are essential for effective communication in English, are complex lexical units formed by combining a main verb and one or more auxiliary units to express meanings that are often idiomatic. For example: look after, give up, turn on, take off, the resulting combination is a new, often idiomatic phraseological verb. Phrasal verbs, which are often idiomatic, can be very confusing, because they have thousands of variants. Indeed, many phrasal verbs are specific variations of the same main verb, which are likely to cause various confusions. Therefore, the complexity of these constructions, due to their idiomatic nature, creates specific difficulties in translation, which do not always correspond directly to the grammatical

structures of other languages, since phrasal verbs are polysemantic phenomena in the semantic system of the English language, that is, one verb can have different meanings in several different contexts. Therefore, it is impossible to translate them word for word. It is no exaggeration to say that translating phrasal verbs into Uzbek is one of the most difficult tasks, as the language does not easily accept such forms. The idiomatic meanings embodied in phrasal verbs are deeply intertwined with the cultural and linguistic context of the English language, and it is necessary to make grammatical and cultural changes in order to create equivalent expressions in Uzbek. Structurally, phrasal verbs are divided into two main types:

1. Separable phrasal verbs: in which a complement can be inserted between the verb and the particle. For example: turn off the light, turn the light off.

2. Inseparable phrasal verbs: in which the preposition is used as a whole with the verb. For example: look after, run into.

It is also divided into three-part phrasal verbs. This type of phrasal verbs consists of a verb + a second complement, i.e. a preposition + an adverb. That is, it is a three-part unit and is used in one complete meaning.

For example: look forward to - to wait with anticipation, get away with - to escape punishment, put up with - to endure, run out of - to finish, keep up with - to reach. According to their meaning, phrasal verbs are divided into two types.

1. Literal phrasal verbs. The meaning of this type of compound verbs can be understood literally. For example: sit down - to sit, go out - to go out.

2. Idiomatic (figurative) phrasal verbs. This type of phrasal verbs has an idiomatic meaning, that is, they cannot be translated literally. For example: give up - to give up, bring up - to bring up.

If we dwell on the semantic and stylistic features of phrasal verbs, phrasal verbs enhance the idiomaticity of the English language. They are often not replaced by a single word, because they retain an emotional and stylistic color. A more effective way to explain this is through examples.

Although the verb give up is a simple equivalent of the verb surrender, the first

is used more in everyday speech, and the second in a formal style. Such features create difficulties for the translator. Because the translator must understand the meaning of each phrasal verb not only lexically, but also contextually and pragmatically. It should be said that stylistically, phrasal verbs are actively used mainly in a colloquial style. They reduce the level of formality in the language, give the text naturalness and simplicity. Therefore, for those who are learning English, knowing phrasal verbs is the key to achieving the level of natural speech. Compound verbs cause many difficulties in some aspects. Especially when working between languages with clear syntactic structures and idiomatic expressions, we may encounter some problems. The Uzbek language is an adjoint language, and its grammatical structure differs sharply from English. The equivalent construction in the Uzbek language Phraseological units are often translated or replaced with completely different expressions. However, this approach can lead to a loss of meaning, because when translated, all the subtle differences that are introduced into the original compound verb are lost, and during the translation process, the translator uses the following methods:

1. Finding a contextual equivalent - choosing a word or phrase with a similar meaning;
2. Descriptive translation: translating by explaining the meaning of the phrase;
3. Understanding phraseological compatibility - using a similar idiomatic expression in the Uzbek language, for example: take off - to fly.

Sometimes, however, there is no complete equivalent of phrasal verbs in the Uzbek language. In this case, the translator relies on the principle of semantic proximity. Therefore, not only grammatical, but also cultural competence is necessary for the translator. Also, the meaning of phrasal verbs is often determined by the context. One verb can mean a completely different meaning in different situations. In translation theory, such cases are called polysemantic units. The translator's task is to determine which meaning is used in which context. Phrasal verbs also have cultural problems. For example, in English, the expression call it a day

means "to end the working day", but if translated literally, a different meaning emerges. Thus, phrasal verbs are not just grammatical phenomena, but linguistic units with cultural connotations. The conjunctive syntax of the Uzbek language requires significant restructuring when translating compound verbs. Unlike English, compound verbs are short and flexible within a sentence, and translations into Uzbek may require additional words or a change in word order to convey the same meaning. That is, when translating English sentences into Uzbek, one of the factors that can be taken into account to find the most accurate translation is the context and meaning of the sentence. Translating English phrases into Uzbek requires a good understanding of the corresponding idioms. This can be difficult, but with practice and knowledge of both languages, it will be easier to convey the meanings of the idioms correctly.

In conclusion, there are significant obstacles to translating phrasal verbs from English into Uzbek due to linguistic, cultural, and syntactic differences between the two languages. Although perfect equivalence is rarely achieved, understanding these obstacles can lead to more effective translation processes. This article has comprehensively covered the complexities of phrasal verbs in English. The analysis shows that phrasal verbs constitute the most active and idiomatic layer of the English language. Their meaning is often not translated literally, but is closely related to the context and cultural factors. Therefore, when translating phrasal verbs into Uzbek, simple grammatical knowledge is not enough - the translator must take into account the principles of semantic analysis, stylistic compatibility, and cultural equivalence. In general, phrasal verbs are important linguistic phenomena that express the naturalness, liveliness, and national character of the English language. Their in-depth study is of not only theoretical but also practical importance for the translator and linguist. In the future, conducting more extensive research on this topic, systematizing the phraseological equivalents of phrasal verbs in the Uzbek language and improving their teaching methodology are important scientific tasks.

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